

Studies on *Phyllanthus emblica* seed oil

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Abstract : GLC has been used to determine the fatty acid profile. The oils due to its saturated/unsaturated fatty acids combine and nutritional properties, have been tried for its possible utility in confectionary (chocolate making) as an alternative to traditional cocoa fat. ¹³C NMR has been used to evaluate the olefinic content of the seed oil. High temperature heating of the oil produces an aldehyde. Physico-chemical properties show variation after heat treatment.

Keywords : Seed oil, *Phyllanthus emblica*.

Introduction

Phyllanthus emblica (Euphorbiaceae) is distributed throughout the state of Madhya Pradesh¹⁻³. It has been reported to be antibacterial⁴ and diuretic⁵. Preliminary investigations including nutritional evaluation on the oil have earlier been carried in our laboratory⁶.

Results and discussion

Oil was obtained from the seeds of *P. emblica* by extraction with petroleum ether with an yield of 15%. Fatty acid profile (GLC) of the oil shows myristic (14 : 0), palmitic (16 : 0) and stearic (18 : 0) acids as the major saturated acids besides oleic (18 : 1) and linoleic (18 : 2) as unsaturated acids. Chemical shift value (¹³C NMR) of C-3 carbon appears at δ 24.8 for both saturated and unsaturated fatty acids, δ 25.7 for C-11 carbons-allylic to double bonds of diene (linoleic 18 : 2) chain and δ 27.3 for two carbons-allylic to double bonds of oleic 18 : 1 and linoleic 18 : 2 acids. Chemical shift values of δ 129.9 and 129.6 belong to olefinic carbons of oleic (C-9, C-10) chain while δ 130.1 and 129.9, δ 128.1 and δ 127.9 belong to olefinic carbons (C-9, C-10 and C-12, C-13) of linoleic chain.

The oil – due to essential fatty acids, non-toxicity and nutritional compatability^{8,9} has been evaluated for its possible use in confectionary. Chocolate has a sizeable market among confections and cocoa butter (*Theobroma cacao* fat) is used for the purpose. Cocoa plantation is costly and the plant is restricted to Southern India. As an alter-

native, *Phyllanthus emblica* fat has been tried, in the present work. It is available locally with appreciable (15%) yield of fat. Solidification characteristics influence the physical properties like gloss, texture and stability of the finished product. The seed fat has slightly different composition than cocoa, however it could, successfully, be used in chocolate making. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) profile of the prepared chocolate (Fig. 1) shows smooth surface. After addition of seeding material, the second SEM profile (Fig. 2) shows irregular slates due to crystallization.

The Differential Scanning Colorimetry (DSC) profile of the sample with seeding material (Fig. 3) shows two

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

endothermic peaks – the first corresponding to unstable form and the second to melting. Same sample after 48 h, shows DSC profile (Fig. 4) with one endothermic peak corresponding to melting with disappearance of the unstable form. Thus, during blooming, large crystals of more stable polymorph remains. The crystallization (bloom) has been enhanced by the addition of seed material (Distearoyl Oleoyl Glycerol) – due to crystal-crystal agitation.

On heating the oil at 180 °C for 4 h and analysis at intervals of every 0.5 h, acid value showed an increase – due to secondary decomposition products of oxidation. Peroxide value showed increase, amount of natural antioxidant in the oil sample is unable to effect inhibition in the formation of peroxides. Decrease in iodine value in-

dicates decrease in unsaturation content – due to destruction of double bonds by oxidation. Viscosity values showed an upward trend with increased time of heating.

Fig. 4

Carbonyl compound formed due to thermal oxidation contribute to unpleasant odour. The carbonyl content reacts with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine to give colored derivative in alkaline medium, which has been measured spectrophotometrically, isopropanol has been used instead of benzene^{10,11} or ethanol¹² as benzene is unecofriendly and ethanol is unsuitable due to sparing solubility of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone in it. The absorbance maximum was observed at 450 nm in the UV spectrum. The carbonyl content has been confirmed to be hexenal, which has been produced from linoleic acid due to thermal oxidation.

Experimental

The oil from the coarse seeds was extracted with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) in a Soxhlet extractor. After determining the physical properties, the fatty oil was saponified in presence of alkali. The saponified mixture of fatty acids were converted to Fatty Acid Methyl Ester (FAME) using anhydrous methanol/H₂SO₄. The Me-ester mixture was separated from other impurities by preparative TLC using diethyl ether : hexane : acetic acid (20 : 80 : 1) as solvent system and finally analysed by GLC (Varian-Vista 6000) with OV 101 column, N₂ carrier gas, F.I.D. using 1 μl sample and a chart speed of 4 mm/min. For ¹³C NMR, JEOL JMNFX 100 spectrometer with gated pulse sequence and data memory with acquisition time of 1 s was used.

Note

For chocolate making 25 part extracted fat, 30 part chocolate liquor (confectionary), 40 part sucrose (A.R.) and 1 part lecithin (Sigma) were pulverized. The sample was observed under scanning electron microscope – SEM (FEI-Philips XL-30). The above preparation was heated to 60 °C (molten) and later cooled to 20 °C (tempering). At this stage 5 part of Distearoyl Oleoyl Glycerol (Sigma) was added as seeding material. The contents were agitated for 5 min. After 15 min, the prepared sample was subjected to SEM. For Differential Scanning Calorimetry, DSC (Seiko 580) instrument was used.

For high temperature heating the oil was subjected to heat at 180 °C for 4 h in an open pan. The oil samples were drawn every 0.5 h for determination of acid value, peroxide value, iodine value and viscosity by standard methods. For determination of carbonyl content, the oil sample was mixed with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (in isopropanol containing HCl) heated for 20 min at 40 °C, cooled and made alkaline (2% KOH in isopropanol). It was centrifuged (2000 rpm) for 5 min at room temperature and absorption spectrum (350–500 nm) of the upper layer was measured with spectrophotometer (UV-Visible 5501 CECIL).

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